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Research Article

IMPACTS OF SUPPLEMENTATION OF LOW DOSE FOLIC ACID AND LOW DOSE HRT AND INFLUENCE OF COMBINED TREATMENT OF HRT AND FOLIC ACID ON THE LEVEL OF PLASMA OF HOMOCYSTEINE IN POST-MENOPAUSAL FEMALES¹Dr Nazakat, ²Dr Sundas Fatima, ²Dr Saulat Shabbir¹Avicenna Hospital Lahore²THQ Hospital Khanpur Rahim Yar Khan**Article Received:** July 2020**Accepted:** August 2020**Published:** September 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: To assess the impacts of HRT (Hormone Replacement Therapy) and supplementation of folic acid level of HCY (Homocysteine) in post-menopausal females.

Methodology: This randomized research work was carried out on 66 menopausal females for two years visiting the Avicenna Hospital Lahore from March 2018 to May 2020. We randomly separated the patients into 4 separate groups. Before examining the plasma level of folate, Albumin, fasting plasma level and total protein, measurement of HCY was performed. The subjects of the 1st groups took 5.0 mg folic acid daily. The patients of 2nd groups received 0/625mg oral conjugated estragon as well as med Roxy progesterone acetate 2.0/5.0 mg daily. The patients of the 3rd group took combination of HRT and folic acid and the patients of the 4th group received the placebo. We measured the fasting plasma Homocysteine after four weeks.

Results: There was significant decrease in the plasma HCY level significantly in the patients of Group-1, Group-2 and Group-3 ($P < 0/05$) after completion of treatment. We found much significant difference between the patients of Group-1, Group-3 ($P = 0/026$) and Group-1, Group-4 ($P = 0/005$) for plasma Homocysteine level.

Conclusion: Treatment with folic acid and HRT can decrease the plasma level of Homocysteine. Combined treatment from both folic acid and HRT is highly effectual as compared to the treatment through supplementation of folic acid and HRT in the decrease of Hyperhomocysteinemia.

Keywords: Folic Acid, Hormone Replacement Therapy, Plasma, Treatment, Supplementation, Menopausal Females.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Nazakat,**

Avicenna Hospital Lahore

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

HCY (Hyperhomocysteinemia) is very significant independent risk factor for the diseases of atherosclerotic as stroke, IHD (Ischemic Heart Disease) and PVD (Peripheral Vascular Disease). There is association of the enhanced level of plasma Homocysteine with the endothelial abnormalities in healthy persons. There is significant low plasma level of Homocysteine in the pre-menopausal females as compared to young males but after the menopause, there is significant increase in the homocystinuria in the females approaching those in males. Alterations in the hormonal status and low folate intake related with age are accountable for this factor. CVD (Cardio-vascular Disease) is the leading cause of high rate of mortality for both males and females in the societies of west and it is highly attributed to lifestyle and age. It is much common disease for the females in post-menopause state. The risk of the diseases of heart is much low in the females as compared to males until the state of after menopause. This alteration in the prevalence of the diseases of heart may have association with the advancement in age, alterations in the hormonal status and some other not known factors [1].

Increased levels of HCY have association with the enhancement in the CHD (Coronary Heart Diseases), endothelial disorders, thrombosis and atherosclerosis. Increase in the intake of HRT and folic acid decreases the circulating Homocysteine levels [2]. Age and gender of the patients as well as circulating levels of B12 and folate have influence of the plasma level of HCY and it is also influenced by the status of estrogen. After state of menopause, there is lost in the protection of CVD because of the deficiency of estrogen. Very simple, supplementation of the folic acid can be advantageous in the protection of the post-menopausal females from CVD [3]. This current research work was carried out to interrogate the influences of folic acid and HRT on the HCY.

METHODOLOGY:

This is a randomized research work. We selected the patients of this research work from the OPD of the Avicenna Hospital Lahore who visited from March 2018 to May 2020. We obtained the written consent from the patients before including them in this research work. We randomly enrolled 66 females in 4 separate groups. We used the ELISA method for the measurement of the level of plasma albumin, folate and total protein. We included the females with normal laboratory test in this research work. We obtained the samples of blood from antecubital veins after overnight fasting in the start of the research work and after completion of four weeks. We stored the sera at -50 centigrade before analysis. There were 16 females in the Group-1 who obtained 5.0mg folic acid daily for four weeks. 18 females of Group-2 took HRT 0/625.0 oral conjugated estrogen in combination with the 2.0/5.0 mg med Roxy progesterone acetate on daily basis for four weeks. Group-3 consisted 18 females who took both 5.0 mg folic acid & HRT for four weeks. 7 females in the Group-4 did not take any medicine as controls. All the patients were taking normal diet and having normal physical activity and all these patients were not on supplementation of B6 and/or B12. Menopausal females without any kidney complications, gastrointestinal infections and CVD were included in this research work. All the females with habit of cigarette smoking, abnormal level of plasma albumin, folate, total protein or having supplementation of B6 or B12 were not included in this current research work. The comparison of the findings of the various groups of patients was carried out with the utilization of the ANOVA and paired t-test. The significance level was set as $P < 0/05$.

RESULTS:

The summary of the findings of this research work is present in Table-1, Table-2 and Table-3.

Table-I: Mean Age, Duration of Menopause, Plasma Albumin, Total Protein and Primary Plasma HCY In Study Groups

Variables	Group1(n=16)	Group2(n=18)	Group3(n=15)	Group4(n=17)	P Value
Mean age(years)	53.31±6.04	54.61±7.01	51.67±4.67	56.18±3.3	0.13
Duration of menopause(yr.)	6.94±3.75	7.33±4.92	5.20±2.91	8±3.24	0.21
Plasma albumin (g/dl)	4.13±1.01	4.39±0.83	3.73±1.01	4.24±0.90	0.48
Plasma total protein (g/dl)	6.39±0.43	6.45±0.62	6.30±0.37	6.26±0.80	0.15
Plasma folate (mg/ml)	6.13±2.5	5.83±2.55	8.35±3.14	7.47±4.47	0.08
Primary HCY (micromol/L)	17.65±6.07	19.50±3.80	19.06±4.41	17.82±5.17	0.63

There was no statistical difference in the average age, menopause duration, level of plasma albumin, folate, total protein and level of plasma HCY in the patients of all groups in the start of this research work. There was decreased level of plasma HCY in the patients of treatment groups ($P < 0/05$).

Table-II: Plasma HCY Level Before and After Study in Four Groups Plasma HCY (Micromol/L) Plasma HCY (Micromol/L) P Value Level Before Treatment Level After Treatment

Group 1	17.65±6.07	11.12±4.25	P=0.002	t=3.70
Group 2	19.5±3.80	10.22±3.22	P=0.000	t=7.58
Group 3	19.06±4.15	7.73±4.21	P=0.000	t=9.43
Group 4	17.82±5.17	18.11±4.85	P=0.603	t=0.531

Combined treatment through supplementation of folic acid and HRT has the ability to decrease the plasma level of HCY as compared to the supplementation of folic acid or HRT alone.

Table-III: Plasma HCY Level Before and After Treatment in Each Group and Other Groups

Groups	Other groups	Mean of HCY (micromol/L)	P value	95% confidence interval	
				Upper bound	Lower bound
Group1	Group2	3.18±1.79	0.297	1.56	7.92
	Group3	5.43±1.87	0.026	0.47	10.4
	Group4	6.38±1.82	0.005	11.19	1.57
Group2	Group1	3.18±1.79	0.297	7.92	1.56
	Group3	2.25±1.82	0.608	2.57	7.08
	Group4	9.57±1.76	0	14.24	4.9
Group3	Group1	5.43±1.87	0.026	10.4	0.47
	Group2	2.25±1.82	0.608	7.08	2.57
	Group4	11.82±1.85	0	16.71	6.93
Group4	Group1	6.83±1.82	0.005	1.57	11.19
	Group2	9.57±1.76	0	4.9	14.24
	Group3	11.82±1.85	0	6.93	16.71

DISCUSSION:

According to the findings of this current research work, supplementation of folic acid and HRT alone or combined can reduce the plasma level of HCY in the post-menopausal females. HAK in his research work conducted in 2001 stated that there is influence of menopause on HCY. After the menopause, high level of HCY is the outcome of the changed status of hormones and low level of folate [3]. There is no fully evaluated data about the influence of the various procedures and formulas for the administration of the HRT on the level of plasma HCY. Majority of the research works designed to assess the impacts of folic acid on the level of plasma HCY [4]. Supplementation of the folic acid (from 500 to 5000 microgram) can decrease the HCY plasma level in the post-menopausal females [5, 6]. It is well evidenced that supplementation of folic acid alone as well as in combination with HRT has much better impacts in decreasing the level of plasma HCY in low status of estrogen following to ovariectomy [3, 4].

Total concentration of HCY from 12.0 to 13.0 micromol/L is defined as moderate HCY, it is important risk factor for vascular brain complications, heart complications and thromboembolic abnormalities

[3]. HCY is syndrome of metabolism which is dependent on the interaction between the diseases of genetic factors, demography, aging and various other factors associated with hormonal changes and nutrition [3, 6]. Therapy of HCY is totally depending upon the administering of the pharmacological folic acid's doses, which has the ability to reduce the concentration of total homocysteine by 25.0% to 30.0%. This reduction, which is mean 3.0 micromol/L, results in the reduction of the risk of IHD (Ischemic Heart Disease) by 11.0% to 16.0%, phlebothrombosis by 25.0% & vascular brain diseases by 19.0% to 24.0% [3]. In current era, there is more attention on the folate's role on the health of public. Villa P conducted a research work in Italy on 20 menopausal females who were present without any history of consumption of anti-hypertension drug or hypoglycemic agent, folic acid low dose can reduce the level of plasma HCY, insulin and it betters the profile of lipids [6].

One research work was performed to assess whether decreasing HCY with folic acid or HRT in the ovariectomized rats could reduce cardiovascular disorders [7]. De Leo discovered that lose dose supplementation of folic acid for 4 weeks decreases

the level of plasma HCY in 18 post-menopause females. This decrease is clearly visible particularly in the females with high level of plasma HCY. The finding of that research is much comparable with the results of this current research work [5]. In this current research work, combined treatment through folic acid and HRT has a significant reduction in the level of HCY as compared to the treatment with folic acid alone, but there was not much significant disparity with the HRT treatment alone. Average level of HCY in the group of supplementations of folic acid (Group-1) was 13.90 microgram/L before start of treatment and 9.30 microgram/L after completion of treatment. There was 30% reduction in the level of HCY.

Although supplementation of HRT combined with folic acid has beneficial impact in decreasing the level of plasma HCY in post-menopausal females. Supplementation of HRT combined with folic acid prevents the incidence of CVD with decrease in the level of HCY. Even though there is no use of HRT in postmenopausal condition for the prevention of CVDs, this is available treatment to prevent the urogenital atrophy and vasomotor symptoms in the duration of menopause. Until the association between the HRT, menopause, folate and homocysteine is completely elucidated with a large number of comprehensive research works, consisting the description, there is recommendation that there should be provision of precise knowledge to the menopausal females with complete risk analysis with the treatment through HRT and patient should be only decision maker to get into the treatment.

CONCLUSION:

There is much better impact of combined treatment through HRT and folic acid to decrease the level of plasma HCY.

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